

Fig. 1. pH-titrations: (A) acid, (B) ligand and (C) metal.

almost regularly. This observation is quite reverse of the same obtained by Nayan and Dey¹⁰ in case of folic acid complexes, showing quite different mechanism for the metal–ligand interaction in case of amethopterin.

The values of formation constants obtained for the metal complexes studied here are very much higher than those reported for the folic acid complexes¹⁰. The observed enhanced stability of amethopterin complexes seems quite logical in the light of higher $\log K_f^H$ value for amethopterin^{8,11}, viz. $\log K_f^H$ for folic acid, 6.55 at 30°, and for AMPGA, 7.65 at 35°; $\log K_1$ for Be^{II}–folic acid, 4.80 at 30°, and for Be^{II}–AMPGA, 7.20 at 35°, at $\mu=0.05 M$.

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Praseodymium(III), Neodymium(III), Samarium(III), Holmium(III) and Erbium(III) Complexes with 3-(3-Hydroxy-2-naphthalideneimino)propanoic Acid and *N*-Sali-cylideneisovaleric Acid as Ligands

(Miss) PREETI MEHTA and R. K. MEHTA*

Department of Chemistry, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

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LANTHANON chelates of ligands possessing oxygen and nitrogen donor atoms find application as bactericides and fungicides. 3-(3-Hydroxy-2-naphthalideneamino)propanoic acid (H_2NP) and *N*-sali-cylideneisovaleric acid (H_2SI) also possess such donor sites. A perusal of the literature has indicated that no studies have been made on Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes with H_2NP and H_2SI . The present paper describes the findings on such compounds.

Experimental

The ligands H_2NP and H_2SI were prepared as reported earlier¹. The solid complexes of H_2NP and H_2SI with the lanthanons under study were prepared by the method reported earlier². The results of elemental analyses, molar conductance and molecular mass are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis and molecular mass data suggest 1 : 2 (metal–ligand) stoichiometry for all the compounds. The conductance data indicate their non-electrolytic nature (Table 1).

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of the complexes (Table 2) showed a shift in band position towards the lower wave numbers as compared to those of the aqua-complexes. The bands observed in the case of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes could be assigned to the transitions from 3H_4 , $^4I_{9/2}$, $^6H_{5/2}$, 5I_8 and $^4I_{15/2}$ (ground levels) to the excited J levels of the respective $4f^n$ configurations. The present data also show that the nephelauxetic values for different J levels vary considerably. The $(1-\beta)$ values are used to estimate Sinha's covalency³ parameter (δ). Another bonding parameter, $b^{1/2}$, which measures the amount of $4f$ orbital–ligand-orbital mixing in these compounds were also calculated. The values of $(1-\beta)$, δ and $b^{1/2}$ at corresponding transitions are also included in Table 2. The positive values for $(1-\beta)$ and δ suggest that the bonding between metal and ligand is covalent as compared to that in the metal–aqua-ions. The average values of δ are positive, but smaller than unity in the case of complexes derived from H_2SI . It indicates weaker covalent bonding in H_2SI complexes than in those of H_2NP complexes. The $b^{1/2}$ values are higher for the H_2NP

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Decomp. temp. °C	Mol. mass Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				ΔM $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$ mol^{-1}
			O	H	N	M	
[Pr(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆)]	305	609 (623)	58.71 (59.91)	3.52 (3.69)	4.28 (4.49)	22.33 (22.47)	3.2
[Nd(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆)]	295	615 (627)	58.37 (59.58)	3.52 (3.56)	4.31 (4.46)	22.73 (22.96)	3.4
[Sm(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆)]	315	621 (633)	52.93 (53.08)	3.49 (3.63)	4.27 (4.42)	23.51 (23.69)	3.3
[Ho(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆)]	276	634 (648)	51.76 (51.85)	3.39 (3.54)	4.19 (4.32)	25.23 (25.46)	3.9
[Er(C ₂₀ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₆)]	300	638 (650)	51.48 (51.69)	3.42 (3.53)	4.19 (4.30)	25.51 (25.69)	4.2
[Pr(C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆)]	325	570 (579)	49.58 (49.74)	4.51 (4.66)	4.69 (4.83)	24.00 (24.17)	4.7
[Nd(C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆)]	310	576 (583)	49.21 (49.39)	4.43 (4.63)	4.61 (4.80)	24.43 (24.69)	5.2
[Sm(C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆)]	280	578 (589)	48.70 (48.89)	4.41 (4.58)	4.62 (4.75)	25.32 (25.46)	5.8
[Ho(C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆)]	295	591 (604)	47.40 (47.68)	4.32 (4.47)	4.46 (4.63)	27.11 (27.31)	6.1
[Er(C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₆)]	305	595 (606)	47.39 (47.52)	4.32 (4.45)	4.50 (4.62)	27.39 (27.55)	6.7

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA AND RELATED BONDING PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Lanthanone (Ln)	λ_{max} (cm ⁻¹)		Assignments	$(1-\beta) \times 10^{-2}$		$\delta(\%)$		$b^{1/2} \times 10^{-1}$	
	Ln(NP) ₂	Ln(SI) ₂		Ln(NP) ₂	Ln(SI) ₂	Ln(NP) ₂	Ln(SI) ₂	Ln(NP) ₂	Ln(SI) ₂
PrIII	22 290	22 350	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	0.75	0.32	0.755 7	0.320 0	0.06	0.03
	21 110	21 170	→ ³ P ₁	1.03	0.78	1.040 7	0.786 1	0.07	0.06
	20 600	20 660	→ ³ P ₀	0.77	0.59	0.776 0	0.590 4	0.06	0.05
	16 810	16 910	→ ¹ D ₂	1.23	0.58	1.345 4	0.585 4	0.08	0.05
NdIII	19 470	19 480	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2} , ³ H _{9/2}	0.30	0.26	0.309 3	0.261 3	0.03	0.03
	18 850	18 970	→ ⁴ F _{7/2} , ³ S _{3/2}	1.39	0.78	1.408 4	0.786 2	0.08	0.06
	17 210	17 240	→ ⁴ F _{9/2}	0.63	0.40	0.634 0	0.401 8	0.05	0.04
	14 520	14 520	→ ⁴ G _{5/2} , ³ G _{7/2} *	0.75	0.75	0.799 4	0.799 4	0.06	0.06
	13 300	13 330	→ ⁴ G _{7/2}	1.12	0.75	1.722 4	0.751 5	0.07	0.06
	12 420	12 450	→ ⁴ G _{9/2}	0.95	0.49	0.979 5	0.598 6	0.07	0.04
SmIII	24 760	24 780	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ F _{9/2}	0.40	0.40	0.402 4	0.406 3	0.03	0.03
	23 700	23 740	→ ⁶ F _{5/2}	0.59	0.38	0.593 5	0.381 9	0.05	0.04
	21 500	21 580	→ ⁴ I _{13/2}	0.60	0.44	0.600 6	0.441 8	0.05	0.04
HoIII	22 330	22 340	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ G ₆ , ⁵ F ₁ *	0.65	0.65	0.651 0	0.651 0	0.05	0.05
	19 080	18 870	→ ⁵ F ₄	0.36	0.28	0.362 3	0.285 1	0.03	0.02
	15 700	15 620	→ ⁵ F ₅ , ⁵ S ₂	1.01	0.67	1.014 7	0.671 3	0.08	0.06
	13 420	13 390	→ ⁵ I ₄	0.86	0.59	0.869 1	0.591 1	0.06	0.04
ErIII	22 210	22 190	⁴ I _{13/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}	1.03	0.87	1.036 8	0.870 6	0.07	0.06
	20 700	20 640	→ ⁴ F _{7/2}	0.78	0.57	0.739 0	0.580 3	0.06	0.05
	19 300	19 300	→ ⁴ H _{11/2}	0.82	0.61	0.823 3	0.612 4	0.05	0.04
	15 370	15 260	→ ⁴ F _{9/2}	0.63	0.38	0.630 0	0.389 1	0.03	0.03

* Red-shift

complexes than that for the H₂SI complexes, which indicates relatively stronger covalent bonding in the former.

The absorption spectra of the Nd^{III} complexes dissolved in dimethylsulphoxide exhibit an appreciable red-shift with respect to aqua-cation. They involve ⁴I_{9/2} → ³G_{7/2}, ⁴G_{5/2} transitions. A red-shift with smaller values for δ were also observed for the ⁵I₈ → ⁵G₆, ⁵F₁ and ⁵F₄ transitions of the Ho^{III} complexes. For the Er^{III} complexes no red-shift was observed for the ⁴I_{13/2} → ³H_{11/2} and ⁴F_{5/2} transitions while the ⁴I_{13/2} → ⁴F_{7/2}, ⁴F_{9/2} transitions

were either unaffected by complex formation or showed a very slight red-shift.

Infrared spectra : In the ir spectra, bands are observed at 3 370, 2 580, 1 690 and 1 610 cm⁻¹ for H₂NP, and 3 390, 2 570, 1 695 and 1 605 cm⁻¹ for H₂SI which correspond to $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$, ν_{COOH} , $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, respectively. An additional band at 1 590 cm⁻¹ corresponding to naphthalene ring⁴ was observed for H₂NP and its complexes. It appears that the phenolic oxygen is intra-molecularly hydrogen bonded to the lone-pair of azomethine N-atom⁵. The ν_{OH} of the ligand around 3 390

370 cm^{-1} shifted to lower frequency range 3 350–330 cm^{-1} suggesting rupture of hydrogen bonding and participation of the phenolic OH in coordination. The ligand band around 2 580–570 cm^{-1} disappears suggesting coordination through the carboxylate group. The $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ moves from 1 610 to 1 580 and from 1 605 to 1 580 cm^{-1} in the H_2NP and H_2SI complexes, respectively, indicating involvement of azomethine nitrogen in coordination. The complexes also showed bands in the region 1 570–1 560 cm^{-1} due to ν_{as} (COO). The appearance of bands in the narrow ranges 415–400 and 522–500 cm^{-1} suggests metal–nitrogen and metal–oxygen bondings⁶ in the complexes. Thus the ligands offered tridentate (O, N, O), chelation to the lanthanide ions to form octahedral complexes.

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Studies on Complexes of Tridentate Schiff Bases derived from 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and Diamines with Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II)

G. P. POKHARIYAL* and P. SINGH**

Chemistry Department, M. M. College, Khakra-201 101

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COUMARIN and its derivatives have been found to exhibit physiological activity and are also extensively used as analytical reagents¹⁻⁴. 7-Hydroxycoumarin known for its antibiotic and antifungal activities^{5,6} having substituents like amino and nitro at position-8 and methyl at position-4, has been investigated for complexing ability^{7,8}. 8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin has been found to exhibit anticoagulant and plant growth regulant property^{9,10}. The present paper deals with the synthesis and characterisation of title metal ions

complexes of Schiff bases derived from 8-acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methyl coumarin and ethylenediamine/propylenediamine.

Experimental

8-Acetyl-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin (AHC) was prepared¹¹ and the other reagents were of A.R. grade. Ethylenediamine (en) and propylenediamine were purified by distillation under reduced pressure. The Schiff bases, *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)ethylenediamine (AHCE) (m.p. 131.5°) and *N*-(8-aceto-7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin)propylenediamine (AHCP) (m.p. 146°) were synthesised by refluxing (30 min) AHC and ethylenediamine/propylenediamine in 1 : 1 molar ratio in ethanol. On cooling, yellow crystalline products were obtained which were filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Complexes were prepared by mixing ethanolic solutions of ligands and metal chlorides in 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 molar ratios. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 1–3 h and then concentrated. On cooling, the complexes were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in air.

Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the ligands and the complexes were estimated by microanalysis. The metal estimations were carried out following standard procedures¹². Magnetic and spectral studies were made as reported earlier¹³. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The molar conductance of the complexes was measured in DMF ($10^{-3}M$) using a Elico CM-82 conductivity bridge with a cell having cell constant of 1.0 cm^{-1} . The molar conductance values of all Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} and Co^{II} complexes were in the range 4–13.6 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating that the complexes are non-electrolytes¹⁴.

Copper(II) complexes: The room temperature μ_{eff} values of Cu^{II} complexes are close to the spin-only value of 1.73 B.M. and indicate the presence of one unpaired electron. The electronic spectra of Cu^{II} complexes show bands in the regions 18 500–19 000, 21 500–22 000 and 24 000–25 000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to the transitions ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$, respectively assuming a square-planar geometry. The appearance of third band may be attributed to the charge transfer transition.

Nickel(II) complexes: In the electronic spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes, three distinct bands appear in the range 10 025–10 660 (ν_1), 16 390–17 950 (ν_2) and 27 025–28 830 cm^{-1} (ν_3), respectively. The latter two bands are characteristics of an octahedral complex¹⁵ which is further confirmed by the ν_2/ν_1 ratio (1.6–1.8).

Cobalt(II) complexes: The magnetic moment values for Co^{II} complexes are in the ranges expected

**Chemistry Department, S. S. V. College, Hapur-245 101.